

Development of flexible simulation tool for analysis of microgrid systems

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Abstract— The paper deals with a modern concept seeking the development of a flexible and reliable tool for analysis of a modern microgrid, including green power generation, electronic conversion, storage and usage. The flexible attribute comes from the real-time nature of the simulation program that will include detailed models for each assembly of the system able to easily transition to HIL testing. The simulation program will be compound of a wind and solar based energy harvesting system, an electronic converter that connects the battery to it and a residential load. These will be modelled in Typhoon HIL environment and the simulation will be running on a Typhoon HIL 604 real-time target. The future of the analysis is to offer the possibility to replace the virtually modelled assemblies with real hardware. In doing so, one can test the entire system based on simulation or a hybrid mixture between simulated and real devices as well as complete real system having only the controller running on the real-time target.

Keywords—microgrid, real-time, HIL, simulation

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays the challenge is to create tools that ease the development of new systems offering fast and efficient prototyping environments. Taking advantage of the power of the newly developed simulation software and real-time targets attached to those, it became quite easy to develop such genuine solutions. More, it is important that these tools to offer the possibility of analysis in real-time as well as to feature fast transitions from pure simulation level testing to Hardware in the Loop one. The transition should be facilitated by direct communication of the real-time platform with the hardware devices and with the simulation program based on a plug & play concept.

The present study is focused on analysis of a complex residential microgrid. This will be composed of a wind turbine and a solar photovoltaic system for energy harvesting, a Li Ion battery with its converter for storage and a load as power user. Preliminary, the complete system will be modeled on the Typhoon HIL real-time target, and in the future is foreseen that the latter one will act only as controller for the real hardware system. It is also foreseen that during the development of the hardware system, different assemblies from the simulation will be replaced firstly with power emulators and later on with their actual hardware homologues.

II. STRUCTURE OF THE ANALYSIS

The system under analysis is depicted in Fig. 1. As it can be seen here, this is the final goal of the study, where, as explained in the introduction section, The Typhoon HIL target remains as general controller of the hardware assemblies or of their emulators.

Fig. 1. Schematic of the proposed system

However, before diving into the actual development of the real hardware, one must perform a deep and accurate analysis of it, ensuring the feasibility of the future system. There are several assemblies and equipment's existing in our university laboratories that will be engaged in this paper, but there were never before connected together and tested as a complete unit. To ensure both success and safety, each assembly will be digitally replicated in the real-time analysis environment and tested at component level. Once this performance is validated, the assemblies will be fuzzed into a system and tested for real-life behavior, using pre-recorded data for both energy production and consumption in different scenarios. Even more, it is intended to asses faults within the simulation to ensure the system's proper response. After all these real-time simulation processes validate the components behavior interconnected into a system, the next step will be

to test the hardware assemblies, again, components based. For this, from the simulation program the digital replica of the component will be replaced with input and output ports connecting the simulation environment to the actual hardware. Once each component is validated, the last step will be to create the complete hardware system and keep on the real-time target only its general controller.

The software and hardware requisites of Typhoon HIL cover all the demands of this study, both for simulation testing as well as for HIL one [1]. In Fig. 2-top a generic structure of the schematic is presented, this being the environment where the user can build its models. Still in Fig. 2-bottom, the SCADA interface is presented, where the user can monitor, control and log data from the simulation or from the HIL testing.

Fig. 2. The Typhoon HIL environment, Schematic Editor (top) and SCADA (bottom)

The simulation tool offer the possibility for a dual method of designing the analysis programs. One allows the user to create signal based models, rooted from mathematical equations. In this case, the level of complexity and accuracy is given by the model's complexity. This method demand the user to have skills and knowledge about mathematically modelling each assembly of the system.

Another approach, more professional and accurate by all means, is to use library elements for each assembly. A wide range of parameters can be used to characterize the hardware. This approach is called power components approach, as the models will exchange virtual powers when operating, contrary to the signal model based ones, that use signals to emphasize energetic quantities. The power based approach allows fast development and then the transition from this modelling to actual HIL testing is even more facilitated as the power modules replicate even the communications of the real hardware.

The development of the simulation model is created in Typhoon HIL Schematics environment, uploaded on a Typhoon HIL 604 real-time target and monitored from Typhoon HIL SCADA environment [2]. Using the data from the real PV system installed in the university area premises, a data file necessary for the simulation program was created using the Typhoon Waveform Generator application. This creates the U-I curve of the PV panels that reach the maximum output power of 3274W at 94V and 34.8A as represented in Fig. 3. When building the circuit, a maximum power point tracking module MPPT was implemented, to make sure that when it is possible, the maximum power is extracted from the PV panels [3]. This is based on ranging the duty cycle of the buck power converter to maximize the extracted power. The duty cycle is computed by perturbation of the extracted power in 0.001 (duty cycle steps) and monitoring the product of the current and voltage.

Fig. 3. U-I curve of the PV panels from Typhoon Waveform Generator application

The circuit consists of the PV panel, the buck converter, an LC filter, a load, contactors that can separate the system components and a Li-Ion battery, rated at 51V and 40Ah, Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Complete simulation model of the system

It has to be mentioned that for the PV (temperature and irradiance), for the wind turbine (wind speed) and for the load (load currents), the data used in the simulation are fetched from real measurements and imported into the simulation environment via look-up-tables. These parameters were fetched from a local building that is inhabited in apartments. Using that particular location, for a range of 24h these parameters were recorded and stored to be applied as inputs to the desired simulation.

The PV model in the circuit is based on the data file generated and reference in SCADA with the temperature

and the irradiance. The buck electronic converter is a standard block from the library in which the PWM internal modulator operated at 10kHz the duty cycle being computed from the MPPT algorithm and sent to the converter. The output LC filter handles the voltage and current harmonics due to the PWM. The values were computed to reach the 10kHz switching frequency. The voltmeters and the amperemeters in the circuit are linked to labels that then are accessible in the SCADA environment for monitoring and recording. The battery is a library component that was parametrized with data from the actual battery in the laboratory. In the future this block will be replaced with a custom made model dedicated to reach larger accuracy compared to the real hardware. The load resistance, at the moment, is linear set at 10ohm, just to validate the system. This will be replaced by a variable power consumption unit reference with actual power consumption recordings.

The simulation program operates at fixed step time, (200e-6s). This is now operational as the model is not very large, but as the complexity and the number of elements will increase, there might be necessary to increase the sampling time as well. In this case, we use 2e-5s or 2e-4s as sample time.

In a preliminary testing situation, the system was started and after a certain time the battery and then the load were connected and disconnected. To make sure the system works fine, at an instance the PV panels were disconnected and the load remained supplied only by the battery. In the picture above, the results ranging on a sample time of 600s were depicted. It can be observed that as the contactors are engaged, the PV delivers power to charge the battery and to supply the load. In case the load is not connected, the current on the battery increases in as the MPPT keeps the PVs at the same maximum power, and the battery does not need to share the current with the load. In case the battery is disconnected, the load is supplied directly from the PVs. In this case, as the power demand is low, the efficiency of the cells will be low as well. If the PVs are disconnected from the system, the battery will deliver all the necessary power to the load. All these scenarios were covered in the above graphs. When the PV current is 0, it means that those are not operational, the same being valid for the battery and the load as well.

In the SCADA environment, the monitoring and the control of the system was developed, Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. SCADA environment for monitoring and recording

There is a main plot in which a real-time monitor of the PV panels point out at each moment the values of the voltage, current and efficiency. Indicators show the instant quantities of the power, voltage and currents on each assembly of the system (PV, battery and load), Fig. 6. The status of the contactors can be manually controlled in order to connect or disconnect parts of the circuit from the PV panels.

Fig. 6. Indicators for instant quantities of the power, voltage and currents on each assembly of the system (PV, battery and load).

In Fig. 7, the variations for these parameters for the range of 24h, expressed in seconds are given. In the top-left plot, the irradiance and the temperature variations for the PV panels are depicted. It must be mentioned that the recordings were taken in February, the reason for the negative and low temperatures. In the top-right plot, the wind speed variation for the same period of 24h is recorded, presenting larger wind speeds during the night and dawn and then lower ones during the daylight. In the bottom plot, for a 2-bedroom apartment, the power and the RMS voltage values were recorded. Using this data, the current load was easy to compute and then used in the simulation as a current source that drains the microgrid. It has to be mentioned that, when analyzing the data for the PV, it is noticeable that the input information is offered rather in steps. This is due to the measurement tool that discretizes the data in hourly mean values. This information will later in the project be replaced by new recording made by a more professional tool able to discretize at second level, just like the wind speed and load data are.

Fig. 7. The Typhoon HiL simulation program for the micro-grid.

Fig. 8. The Typhoon HiL simulation program for the micro-grid

The wind turbine system is depicted in Fig. 8. The MPPT controller computes the speed and torque references to be sent to the FOC controller [4]. Depending on the wind speed, the produced power is higher during the night, and as the daylight comes in, the wind speed decreases as the power does too.

III. MICROGRID HARDWARE COMPONENTS

The proposed microgrid system consist of a load acting as a power user, a Li-ion battery with its converter for storage, a wind turbine and solar photovoltaic system for energy harvesting [5]. In the beginning, the entire system will be simulated using the Typhoon HIL real-time target; it is anticipated that in the future, the latter will just serve as a controller for the actual hardware system. Additionally, it is anticipated that as the hardware system is developed, certain simulation-based assemblies will be swapped out for power emulators initially, and then for their real hardware equivalents.

Next, the hardware components that will be integrated into the proposed microgrid solution will be presented.

A. Battery pack development and testing

The most expensive component of a system which requires energy storage is the *battery pack*. It is an intricate

system with many different parts. These are a few of the crucial elements. The crucial part of a battery pack are the cells. The chemistry of the cell is the combination of materials that make it up. The most widely used chemistry today is the lithium-ion cell, or Li-ion cell. A battery pack was built with Lithium-ion battery cells from Panasonic, type NCR18650BD connecting 14 cells in series, and 12 cells in parallel obtaining a voltage of 48 V. The main parameters of the cells are presented in the following table and Fig. 9 shows the battery pack with cells connected to series using spot welder for nickel strips.

TABLE I. LI-ION BATTERIES SPECIFICATIONS[6]

Parameter	Value
Nominal Voltage (V)	3.60
Maximum Charging Voltage (V)	4.2
Capacity(min.) (mAh)	3030
Capacity(typ.) (mAh)	3180
Maximum current (A)	6.5
Minimum voltage (V)	2.5

Fig. 9. Battery pack with all connections made

A key component of an energy storage system is the *battery management system* (BMS). Monitors important characteristics like voltages, currents, and temperatures, the BMS safeguards cells. It interacts with various systems, including temperature control and oversees cell balancing, which keeps the cells operating at their best voltage. It also has safety features that can turn off the battery in an emergency.

The BD6A20S12P Active Balancer BMS (Fig. 10) is used for battery management system. It is equipped with advanced features such as voltage collection, active large current balancing, overcharge, overcurrent, overtemperature protection, Coulombmeter, Bluetooth connectivity, GPS remote, and many more [7]. This BMS is compatible with lithium ternary, lithium iron phosphate, and other battery types.

Fig. 10. BD6A20S12P Active Balancer BMS and information available through the phone application[7]

Before fixing the battery pack in a metal box for security reasons, a series of tests were carried out. In the first stage using a programmable current source, the batteries were discharged with a current of 20 A until the voltage on each cell reached 3.2V, after which they were charged with the same current up to the maximum charging voltage recommended by the manufacturer (4.2 V). This series of tests was repeated 3 times during which the temperature indicated by the BMS sensors and the temperature measured with the help of a thermal imaging camera were constantly monitored.

The second stage of the tests consisted of charging and discharging the battery at 1C rating (40A) for a duration of half an hour, during which the temperature of the cells or of a possible faulty welding was also monitored.

The third test stage consisted of charging and discharging the battery at 1.5C rating (60A) for a duration of 20 minutes, during which the temperature of the cells was also monitored.

During the tests at 1C rating, the cell temperature was 46 degrees Celsius, and at 1.5C rating, the maximum temperature recorded was 58 degrees Celsius (see Fig. 11). This demonstrates a good functionality of the battery pack. The BMS also carried out cell balancing and disconnected the battery if the voltage exceeded the set minimum and maximum threshold. In Fig. 11 screenshots of the programmable power source and thermal imaging camera during battery pack testing are shown.

After carrying out the tests to verify the good functionality of the battery pack and the BMS, they were inserted into a metal box, leaving only the quick connection terminals to the power circuit and the on/off button of the BMS outside. To increase safety, a 63A fuse has been provided between the positive terminal of the battery and the external terminal.

Fig. 11. Screenshots of thermal imaging camera monitoring battery pack tested at 1C (a) and 1.5C (b)

B. Solar Charge Controller

To ensure that the developed battery system is charged precisely and efficiently a Morningstar's TriStar MPPT-30 (Fig. 12) solar controller with TrakStar Technology™ will be integrated. The converter is equipped with an advanced maximum power point tracking (MPPT) battery charger for off-grid photovoltaic (PV) systems with PV array max power (Pmp) up to 1.6 kW. The controller provides the industry's highest peak efficiency of 99% and significantly less power loss compared to other MPPT controllers [8]. Detailed battery programming options allow for advanced battery support for the latest Lithium, Nickel Cadmium, and Lead Acid battery types. The TriStar MPPT features a smart tracking algorithm that maximizes the energy harvest from

the PV by rapidly finding the solar array peak power point with extremely fast sweeping of the entire I-V curve. This product is the first PV controller to include on-board Ethernet for a fully web-enabled interface and includes up to 200 days of data logging. The Morningstar's TriStar MPPT-30 solar charge controller main features are displayed in Table II.

Fig. 12. Maximum power point tracking controller TS-MPPT-30 [8]

TABLE II. SPECIFICATIONS OF TS-MPPT-30 [8]

Parameter	Value
Charge Rating	30 amps
Max. PV Open Circuit Voltage (Voc)	150 volts
Nominal Battery Voltage	12, 24, 36, or 48V
Nominal max. Operating Power* – 12 volt battery	400W
Nominal max. Operating Power* – 24 volt battery	800W
Nominal max. Operating Power* – 48 volt battery	1600W
Peak efficiency	99%
Battery Operating Voltage Range	8-72Vdc
Voltage Accuracy (12/24V)	<=0.1% +/- 50mV
Voltage Accuracy (48V)	<=0.1% +/- 100mV
Operating Temperature Range	-40 C to +45C

C. HYBRID SYSTEM - PV panel CanadianSolar CS3K-300P & Joliet wind turbine 1 kW

The laboratory disposes of a solar photovoltaic system composed of 12 high efficiency poly module solar panels (Fig. 13) and a Joliet wind turbine of 1 kW that can be used for a hybrid system. The main features of the PV panels are displayed in Table III.

TABLE III. SPECIFICATIONS OF CANADIAN SOLAR CS3K-300P [9]

Parameter	Value
Solar panel type	CanadianSolar CS3K-300P
Nominal Max. power	300W
Optimum operating voltage	32.4V
Optimum operating current	9.18A
Open circuit voltage	39.3V
Open circuit current	9.65A
Maximum system voltage	IEC1000V & UL1000V
Maximum series rating	30A

Fig. 13. PV panels (exposure at 12:30 p.m.)

The physical model of the wind turbine is mounted on the building of UTCN (Fig. 14), at an approximate distance of 30 m above the ground and near the top of the Feleac hill (elevation ~ 430 m). However, in this location, the wind speed has not an high annual average. The main features of the wind turbine are displayed in Table IV.

TABLE IV. SPECIFICATIONS OF JOLIET WIND TURBINE OF 1 kW

Parameter	Value
Model	Joliet wind turbine of 1 kW
Rated power (W)	1000
Generator	Three phase permanent magnet
Blades material	Fiber glass
Number of blades	3
Diameter (m)	2.7
Area (m ²)	5.7
TSR	6
Rated voltage (DCV)	48
Rated voltage (ACV)	68
Rated current (DCA)	21
Rated current (ACA)	15
Rated speed (rpm)	400
Max speed (rpm)	500
Weight	34

Fig. 14. Joliet wind turbine of 1 kW mounted on rooftop

D. Wind MPPT Hybrid Charge Controller

To ensure that the developed battery system is charged precisely and efficiently from the wind turbine Mars Rock 3000W Wind Solar Hybrid MPPT Charge Controller will be integrated in the system, Fig. 15. The device is workable for sealed (GEL, Lead-Acid) & lithium battery [10]. Many parameters can be set such as system voltage, battery type, breeze charging etc. It was specially designed to be suitable for household residential power systems. The main features are displayed in Table V.

TABLE V. MAIN DATA OF WIND MPPT CHARGE CONTROLLER [9]

Parameter	Value
Max input	0 ~ 1500 W(wind) & 0 ~ 1500 W(solar)
Voltage	12/24/48 V
Charge current	30 A(DC)
Brake	Start 60V AC; Recover 54V AC;
MPPT	34V AC
DC Load	Out power 0 – 480W
Temperature	Working -20°C - 55°C
Maximum series rating	30A
Conversion efficiency	> 98%

Fig. 15. Mars Rock 3000W Wind Solar Hybrid MPPT Charge Controller

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This study aims creating a microgrid compound of existing elements to operate together. The goal is preliminary to test their behavior as one unit, seek for certain incompatibilities, solve those and then apply the proper control functionalities to the final testbed. The real time simulation performed on Typhoon HIL, proves that the system works fine, both from simulation program's perspective as well as from testing the entire environment's operation for a real scenario. Future simulations will regard several tests with different loads and environmental conditions.

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